

Study of expected LR in most common pedigree structures: A tool for decision making in forensic genetics

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Abstract

In a missing person search, DNA from an unidentified person is compared with DNA from relatives of the missing person through the kinship test. This allows computing the statistical weight of the evidence using the likelihood ratio approach. Despite the fact that the method is widely accepted, a lack of enough DNA data, due to the few or distant relatives of the missing person, can produce misleading results. For this reason, it is crucial for forensic practitioners to know if the number of relatives data is enough to obtain consistent results when a kinship test is performed. This means high LR when the unidentified person is the missing person, and very low LR when it is not. In this work, we exhaustively simulate different pedigree structures in order to provide expected LR values under both scenarios. We hope that forensic practitioners will find this useful for decision-making.

Keywords: Statistical power, kinship test, Missing Person, disaster victim identification

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1. Introduction

In the search for missing persons, kinship testing using DNA has become a fundamental tool in forensic genetics. In such cases, DNA from an unidentified person (UP) is compared with DNA from the relatives of the missing person (MP), allowing the calculation of the statistical weight of the evidence using the likelihood ratio approach (LR) [1], [2]. This method, widely accepted in forensic science, provides a probabilistic framework to evaluate two competing hypotheses: H_1 , where the UP is the MP, and H_2 , where the UP is not the MP. However, several challenges arise when the number of available relatives or their genetic proximity to the MP is limited, which can lead to inconclusive or misleading results, complicating the identification process.

The need to improve the reliability of kinship tests has been well documented in previous studies [3]–[5]. Early works by Evett and Weir laid the foundation for using Bayes' theorem to interpret forensic evidence, particularly through the calculation of likelihood ratios in kinship and paternity testing scenarios [6], [7]. More recent advances have further refined the statistical models used to evaluate DNA evidence in disaster victim identification (DVI) [8], [9]. Other studies demonstrated how genetic and nongenetic data could be integrated to strengthen identification conclusions, especially in cases where DNA alone might be insufficient or compromised [3], [10], [11]. In addition, different studies have explored the effects of varying pedigree structures on the reliability of kinship tests, underlining the importance of understanding the limitations imposed by distant or limited familial data [12], [13].

Despite the progress made in understanding these limitations, the problem of determining whether available familial DNA data are sufficient to produce reliable LR values persists in common forensic scenarios [14], [15]. Specifically, forensic practitioners need to know when the inclusion of a particular set of relatives will produce consistently high LR values under H_1 (when the UP is the MP) and low LR values under H_2 (when the UP is not the MP). Misleading results can arise if genetic data are sparse or distant relatives are involved, potentially leading to false identifications or missed matches [16], [17].

In this study, our objective is to address this gap by exhaustively simulating the expected LR across various common pedigree structures. By exploring different familial configurations and their associated LR values under both H_1 and H_2 , we provide a comprehensive framework to assess the sufficiency of relative data in kinship testing. This

approach is designed to guide forensic experts in determining when the available evidence is likely to yield conclusive results, thus enhancing decision-making in complex forensic cases. The findings of these simulations are expected to assist forensic professionals in evaluating DNA evidence more effectively, particularly in challenging scenarios where the number of relatives or the strength of genetic relationships is limited.

2. Methods

In this study, we used two complementary approaches to analyze the likelihood of the kinship test in MP cases. First, we performed 50,000 LR simulations for 34 different family configurations, grouped into four main categories: (i) nuclear family (e.g. parent-child), (ii) half-siblings (individuals sharing only one parent), (iii) avuncular relationships (uncle-niece/nephew or first cousins), and (iv) grandparent-grandchild relationships. These configurations represent realistic family structures that could be encountered in forensic cases. In all cases, 22 STR markers from the global allele frequency database were used. The database is publicly available at: <https://leapdna.org/>.

The simulations were carried out using the R packages *misptools* [18] and *forrel* [19], where we calculated the LR for each family configuration. The LR measures the likelihood of observing genetic data under two hypotheses: H_1 (the unidentified person, UP, is the MP) and H_2 (the UP is not the MP). We report the median of \log_{10} (LR) with a confidence interval of 99%. This approach allowed us to simulate how genetic evidence from relatives could support or refute a match between the UP and the MP.

In addition to the simulation-based approach, we used the "Vínculos" application (<https://vinculosgeneticos.netlify.app/>), which applies an additive kinship score to assess the likelihood of family relationships. This method considers specific restrictions, such as the number and type of relatives that can be used for identification, providing an additional layer of analysis. The combination of both methodologies, simulations and the Vínculos app, allowed us to explore the strengths and limitations of each approach in the context of missing person identification.

3. Results

The simulated configurations are shown in Figures 1 to 4, representing nuclear families, half-siblings, avuncular relationships, and grandparent-grandchild relationships.

Figure 1. Nuclear configuration, results using the Argentine frequency database, 22 markers. Squares represent male individuals, circles represent females, the missing person is indicated in red, and individuals whose genotype is available are marked with stripes. For example, in pedigree 1, there is a son (3), his mother (2), and his father (1). Only the mother is genotyped.

Figure 1 illustrates nuclear family configurations, where only first-degree relatives are genotyped. In these cases, the missing person could be the parent or the child, and we simulated multiple scenarios where the genetic data of one or both parents were available. Log10(LR) ranged from 6.73 to 19.96 in these pedigrees, with higher scores and log10(LR) values observed when the genotypes of both parents were available. For example, Pedigree 3, which includes both parents and the missing child, showed a score of 20 and a log10(LR) of 19.96, indicating a strong genetic match between relatives and MP under H1.

In Figure 2, we explore the half-sibling configuration, where the genetic relationship between relatives and the missing person is slightly more distant than in nuclear families. The Log10(LR) in these config-

urations were generally lower than those in Figure 1, ranging from 2.99 to 7.92. As shown in Pedigree 11, where only one half-sibling is genotyped, the score was 3.0, resulting in a log10(LR) of 2.99, demonstrating a moderate likelihood of a match. These findings highlight the importance of genotyping multiple relatives to increase LR and strengthen the conclusion under H1.

Figure 2. Half-siblings configuration, results using the Argentine frequency database, 22 markers. Squares represent male individuals, circles represent females, the missing person is indicated in red, and individuals whose genotype is available are marked with stripes.

Figure 3 shows avuncular relationships, such as uncle-niece/nephew or first cousins. In these configurations, the log10(LR) values ranged from 1.79 to 4.83, indicating weaker support for a match compared to nuclear family or half-sibling configurations. For example, Pedigree 26, where an uncle and a niece are genotyped, yielded a score of 3.0 and a log10(LR) of 2.89. These results suggest that avuncular relationships may provide limited support for kinship

testing unless additional relatives are available for genotyping.

Figure 3. Avuncular configuration, results using the Argentine frequency database, 22 markers. Squares represent male individuals, circles represent females, the missing person is indicated in red, and individuals whose genotype is available are marked with stripes.

Lastly, Figure 4 presents the relationships between grandparents and grandchildren, where the log₁₀(LR) ranged from 1.76 to 6.14. These relationships, though slightly more distant than nuclear families, still offer valuable genetic information for identification purposes. For example, Pedigree 30, where both grandparents are genotyped, showed a score of 6.0 and a log₁₀(LR) of 6.14, suggesting that grandparent-grandchild relationships can produce sufficiently high LR values, particularly when multiple relatives are genotyped.

Figure 4. Grandparents configuration, results using the Argentine frequency database, 22 markers. Squares represent male individuals, circles represent females, the missing person is indicated in red, and individuals whose genotype is available are marked with stripes.

The results of these simulations indicate that closer family relationships, such as nuclear families, tend to produce higher LR values, increasing the likelihood of correctly identifying the missing person under H₁. However, more distant relationships, such as half-siblings or avuncular relationships, still provide valuable information, though the LR may be lower. Inclusion of multiple genotyped relatives in any given pedigree improves the reliability of the LR, offering stronger evidence for or against a match.

4. Conclusions

This study shows the critical role that pedigree structure plays in kinship testing for missing person identification. Through our simulations, we found that closer family relationships, such as those in nuclear families, consistently produce higher likelihood ratio (LR) values, providing stronger genetic evidence under the hypothesis that the unidentified person is the missing person. Pedigrees involving both parents or multiple first-degree relatives tend to offer the most conclusive results, with high log₁₀(LR) values indicating strong support for identification.

In contrast, more distant relationships, such as half-siblings, avuncular, and grandparent-grandchild configurations, while still valuable, typically result in lower LR values. These configurations may require additional relatives to be genotyped to achieve sufficiently robust results. However, our findings show that even with limited or distant family data, kinship testing remains a powerful tool for missing person identification when evaluated with appropriate statistical models.

By simulating different family structures and genotyping conditions, this study provides forensic practitioners with valuable guidance on how to approach complex kinship testing scenarios, particularly when working with limited or distant genetic data.

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